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РЕАКЦИИ ГЕТЕРОЦИКЛИЗАЦИИ АМИНОВ И АМИДОВ С МОНО- И БИФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫМИ СОЕДИНЕНИЯМИ

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REACTIONS OF HETEROCYCLIZATION OF AMINES AND AMIDES WITH MONO- AND BIFUNCTIONAL COMPOUNDS

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Аннотация

Исследованы реакции гетероциклизации аминов и амидов с моно- и бифункциональными соединениями. Проведены реакции циклоконденсации мочевины и тиомочевины с гидрохиноном проводили в стационарных условиях. Синтезированы 5-гидрокси-1,3-бензоксо-2-тион с выходом 92% от теории, и 5-гидрокси-1,3-бензоксо-2-он с выходом 94% от теории. Синтезированы индол и его производные реакцией анилина и его производных с гликолями и триолами при температуре 250-600°C и давлении 1,1·10⁵-1,10⁷ Па в присутствии катализаторов (CdO, ZnO, PbO₂, Al₂O₃, BO₃). Найдены оптимальные условия процесса и предложена вероятная схема стадии образования индола.

Abstract

The reactions of heterocyclization of amines and amides with mono- and bifunctional compounds have been investigated. Cyclocondensation reactions of urea and thiourea with hydroquinone were carried out under stationary conditions. Synthesized 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione with a yield of 92% of theory, and 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-one with a yield of 94% of theory.

Indole and its derivatives have been synthesized by the reaction of aniline and its derivatives with glycols and triols at a temperature of 250-600°C and a pressure of 1.1·10⁵-1.10⁷ Pa in the presence of catalysts (CdO, ZnO, PbO₂, Al₂O₃, BO₃). The optimal conditions of the process are found and a probable scheme of the stage of indole formation is proposed.

Ключевые слова: гидрохинон, мочеви́на, тиомочеви́на, циклоконденсация, индол, синтез, этиленгликоль, одностадийный метод, анилин, катализаторы, гетероциклизация, N-аминофенилэтанол, N-виниланилин.

Keywords: hydroquinone, urea, thiourea, cyclocondensation, indole, synthesis, ethylene glycol, one-step method, aniline, catalysts, heterocyclization, N-aminophenylethanol, N-vinylaniline.

Introduction. The most important areas of modern ecology include the production of effective plant growth bio stimulators and bio fertilizers, the use of which is aimed at solving many environmental problems associated with the preservation of useful biota in agro landscapes and the production of environmentally friendly products. Traditional technologies for the of such synthetic plant bio stimulants as gibberellin, indoleacetic acid, and many others include the use of expensive raw materials, are complex and multi-stage synthesis, are environmentally unsafe, and require waste disposal.

A promising direction for solving this problem is the creation of environmentally friendly technologies for the production of plant growth bio stimulators and bio fertilizers, the raw materials of which are agricultural and industrial waste [1, 14.]

Natural plant growth regulators include phytohormones that are formed in the plant itself and are involved in the regulation of metabolism at all stages of its life. Modern technologies of plant growth bio regulators are aimed at obtaining known phytohormones by synthetic methods, as well as directed synthesis of growth bio regulators that have no analogues in nature and are distinguished by a high level of efficiency in practical application in agriculture.

The problems that exist in this case are mainly related to the choice of raw materials, their rational use, the development of waste-free technologies of growth bio regulators with directed physiological activity, the use of which in the field of agricultural crop production will ensure the production of environmentally friendly products [2, 4].

The world production of photoactive compounds, among which the main place is occupied by herbicides, is about 60% of the market of agrochemical preparations [3, 6, 11-12]. Plant growth regulators are less significant, although it is precisely such compounds that most of all correspond to modern trends in the transition from drugs that destroy weeds to compounds with regulatory properties that can intensify the development of cultivated plants and inhibit the development of weeds or ensure the selectivity of herbicides in their formulations.

At the same time, growth regulators that induce the resistance of cultivated plants to the action of herbicides can be used at various stages of their growth and development [4–5, 11, 13].

One of the most extensive sections of organic chemistry is the section of the chemistry of heterocyclic compounds, which has been widely developed in the last thirty years. This, in particular, is evidenced by the fact that more than half of these publications in scientific journals in organic chemistry are currently works on the chemistry of heterocyclic compounds.

Heterocyclic compounds are obtained by heterocyclization of nitrogen-containing nucleophiles with

mono- and bi functional compounds, which is the most convenient method for the synthesis of the latter.

Nitrogen and oxygen-containing heterocyclic compounds of the pyrrole and indole series are potential raw materials for the production of drugs, continuous and selective pesticides, and plant growth stimulants.

The wide industrial application of nitrogen-containing heterocycles is delayed due to the lack of convenient and cheap methods for their synthesis.

In Uzbekistan, the production of carbamide, thio-carbamide, aldehydes - formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, crotonaldehyde, etc., is well established, which is currently little used. More than 500 thousand tons of urea, 1.0 thousand tons of thiourea, over 20 thousand tons of acetaldehyde, and 7 thousand tons of formaldehyde are produced annually.

In this regard, it is of interest to develop new nitrogen- and oxygen-containing heterocycles based on this raw material.

At present, ammonia compounds, fatty and aromatic amines, nitriles, oximes, hydrazine and its derivatives, amides, thioamides, etc. are used as a nitrogen-containing source [7–9, 12].

In order to develop the chemistry of heterocyclic compounds, to develop new, efficient, convenient, low-step methods for the synthesis of nitrogen- and oxygen-containing heterocycles, we study the heterocyclization reactions of amines and amides with mono- and bifunctional compounds [10–11].

Experimental technique: 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione is a highly effective cotton seed treater. It has been tested for a number of years at the Institute of Genetics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, it was found that when cotton seeds are treated with 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione at a consumption rate of 5.0–10 g/t, the yield increases to 5 q/ha. 5-Hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione was previously synthesized by the condensation of n-quinone with thiourea. We have improved the synthesis method. Instead of n-quinone, we used a more affordable product, hydroquinone.

The process of cyclocondensation of urea and thiourea with hydroquinone was carried out under stationary conditions. Reactions were studied in 2-n hydrochloric acid and glacial acetic acid.

7.6 g (0.1 mol) of thiourea, 11 g (0.1 mol) of hydroquinone, 20 ml of hydrochloric acid, 80 ml of water, 60 ml of acetic acid were placed in a round-bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and an air condenser. With constant stirring, the reaction components were heated in a water bath at a temperature of 90–95 °C for 2 hours. 13.9 g of product were isolated. Yield 92% of theory.

Under similar conditions, 14.2 g of the product was obtained from 6 g (0.1 mol) of urea. Yield 94% of theory.

The reactions go according to the scheme:

where X = S, (I) - 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione; X = O, (II) - 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-one.

The resulting reaction products were washed with an aqueous solution of ethanol and dried in an oven at a temperature of 100–105 °C.

The yield of product (I) is 92 %; (II) - 92 – 94 % of theory. The composition and structure of the synthesized products were established using IR spectroscopy and elemental analysis data.

Elemental analysis of data:

Product (I) Product (II)

Calculated,% Found,% Calculated,% Found,%

C = 55.63 C = 55.60 C = 51.219 C = 50.93

H = 3.311 H = 3.301 H = 2.994 H = 3.01

N = 9.271 N = 9.110 N = 8.383 N = 8.371

In the IR spectrum of the product (I) and (II), absorption bands were found in the region of 3400 - 3200 cm^{-1} related to the stretching vibrations of the OH - group; deformation vibrations of NH-groups; in the region of 1571 - 1508 cm^{-1} to the stretching vibrations of the CH - group.

The material balance of the calculation of the initial substances (Table 1) and the finished product and the basic technological scheme for the production of 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione (Fig. 3) are given below:

Table 1

Material balance

№	Components	Loaded, kg	Received, kg
1.	hydroquinone	115,0	-
2.	thiourea	115,0	8,0
3.	Hydrochloric acid	100,0	100,0
4.	Acetic acid	70,0	70,0
5.	Ammonia	-	17,0
6.	Hydrogen	-	2,0
7.	5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione	-	189
	Total	395	395

The operational amount of thiourea and hydroquinone enters the reactor (pos. P5). There, with vigorous stirring, add 2N hydrochloric acid and add glacial acetic acid in 40-50 minutes. The reaction mixture is heated for 2 hours at a temperature of 80 – 90 °C. The precipitate is filtered off after 12 hours on a druk filter

(pos. DF-6). The precipitate is washed with water and dried in a dryer (pos. T 7). The finished product is packaged in polyethylene barrels with a capacity of 250 ml. Yield 92.8 %. Melting point 175.20 °C (literature data: $t_m = 125.60$ °C).

Figure 3. Principal process flow diagram for the production of 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thion

E-1 - container for hydrochloric acid; E-2 - container for acetic acid; B-3, B-4 - bunkers for hydroquinone and thiourea; P-5 - reactor; DF-6 - druk filter; T-7 - dryer; E-8, E-9, E-10 - containers for the finished product.

Experiments on the synthesis of indole from aniline and ethylene glycol were carried out in a reactor, which is a hollow stainless steel tube with a mesh for a catalyst 30 × 450 mm in size. To maintain the set temperature, the reactor is equipped with an external electric heater, which is controlled using a laboratory autotransformer.

The temperature is measured by a thermocouple with a millivoltmeter. During the experiments, the vapor-gas mixture formed as a result of the reaction enters the refrigerator from the reactor and the condensed vapor-gas mixture passes through the refrigerator, the

condensate flows into the receiver, and the remaining vapor-gas mixture is collected in traps cooled from the outside.

For the heterocyclization process, the catalysts were prepared in the following order: 120 ml of 3-5 % hydrofluoric acid was added to 113.4 g of aluminum hydroxide. To the resulting suspension with stirring was added 10 g of zinc oxide and aluminum fluoride, 4 g of chromium oxide. The resulting mass was stirred, molded, dried and calcined as described above. The finished catalyst has the composition, wt.%: ZnO - 10.0; AlF₃ - 10.0; Cr₂O₃ - 4.0; Al₂O₃ - 76.0.

This method prepared 11 types of catalysts, the composition and properties of which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Composition and Properties of the Developed Catalysts for the Heterocyclization of Aniline with Ethylene Glycol

Catalyst	Composition, % mass	Bulk weight, g/cm ³	Specific surface, m ² /g	Average pore radius,	Mechanical strength, kg/cm ²	Duration of work before re-generation, hour
I	ZnO - 12,0, AlF ₃ - 8,0, K ₂ SiF ₆ - 4,0, Al ₂ O ₃ - 76,0	0.547	210	40	31	48
II	CuCl ₂ - 5,0, AlF ₃ - 5,0, Cr ₂ O ₃ - 5,0, ZnO - 5,0, Al ₂ O ₃ - 80,0	0.580	136	50	27.3	54
III	AlF ₃ - 5,0, Cr ₂ O ₃ - 5,0, ZnO - 5,0, CdF ₂ - 5,0, Al ₂ O ₃ - 80,0	0.554	176	60	39	62
IV	CuCl ₂ - 5,0, CdF ₂ - 5,0, AlF ₃ - 3,0, ZnO - 4,0, Al ₂ O ₃ - 83,0	0.56	203	50	17.3	80
V	CdF ₂ - 5,0, ZnO - 4,0, AlF ₃ - 3,0, Cr ₂ O ₃ - 5,0, Al ₂ O ₃ - 83,0	0.59	210	40	57.4	45
VI	CdF ₂ - 6,25 ZnO - 6,25 AlF ₃ - 3,5 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 6,25 CuCl ₂ - 6,25 Al ₂ O ₃ - 71,5	0.655	172	50	45.0	40
VII	ZnO - 10,0 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 10,0 Al ₂ O ₃ - 80,0 CH ₃ COOH - 5 %	0.715	-	-	30	73
VIII	ZnO - 5,0 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 5,0 NiF ₂ ·2H ₂ O - 10,0 Al ₂ O ₃ - 80,0	0.680	252	45	25.7	70
IX	ZnO - 10,0 AlF ₃ - 3,0 NiF ₃ - 5,0 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 5,0 Al ₂ O ₃ - 77,0	0.670	245	40	26.0	58
X	ZnO - 10,0 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 10,0 AlF ₃ - 7,0 Al ₂ O ₃ - 80,0 HF - 5 %	0.610	223	40	39.4	65
XI	ZnF ₂ - 10,0 ZnO - 3,0 Cr ₂ O ₃ - 3,0 Al ₂ O ₃ - 84,0	0.814	132	55-60	46.0	79

Results and discussion. The process of cyclocondensation of aniline with ethylene glycol is a complex parallel research process that includes the stages of dehydration, dehydrogenation and dehydrocyclization. When selecting a catalyst, the role of each component in the activation of individual stages of the process was taken into account.

According to the literature, it is known that aluminum, cadmium, iron, and zinc fluorides hydrolyze during drying and calcination of the catalyst to form compounds such as Al(OH)F₂, Al(OH)₂F, Cd(OH)F, Fe(OH)F, etc. These compounds create active sites on the surface of the catalyst. X-ray analysis proved that similar hydroxyfluorides are also formed when using acetic acid:

It was found that the activity of the catalyst largely depends on the mode of calcination. The calcination of catalysts above 450 °C leads to a decrease in activity. The reason for this is mainly the decomposition of hydroxyfluorides according to the scheme:

The resulting oxides of cadmium, aluminum, and other metals are less active in catalysis. Since the starting amines used in the synthesis of indole and its derivatives are organic bases, one of the main factors determining the course of the reaction is the acidity of the catalysts used.

The use of fluoride catalysts - aprotic Lewis acids in the synthesis of indoles provides a good yield of end products. Fluorides impart high thermal stability and stability to catalysts.

The service life of the investigated samples of catalysts in one cycle is 40 - 80 hours, which fully meets the requirements for industrial catalysts.

Zinc-chromium-aluminum catalysts modified with various additives are very resistant to catalytic poisons; after regeneration at a temperature of 450-500 °C with atmospheric oxygen, they quickly restore their original activity.

It has been experimentally established that the synthesis of indole from aniline and ethylene glycol can

be successfully carried out using a catalyst containing zinc compounds with sufficient acidity. These requirements are met by the zinc-chromium-aluminum (CHA-X) catalyst developed by us, promoted to 7 % wt. aluminum fluoride. The CHA catalyst has sufficient activity and stability and it works in one cycle with a constant activity up to 60 hours.

Liquid reaction products of aniline with ethylene glycol were analyzed on an Agilent Technology GC/MS AT 5973 N chromat-mass spectrometer according to the DRUGSP-SHORT.M method using a capillary column 30 m × 0.25 mm in size with 5% phenylmethylsiloxane at an injector temperature of 280 °C, the sample size is 1 μl (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Chromate-mass spectrometer of liquid products of the reaction of aniline with ethylene glycol.

The conditions of the gas chromatography-mass spectrum: temperature 280 °C, when programming the temperature of the thermostat of the column from 70 to 280°C, the sample size is 1 μl.

The selectivity of the formation of the above compounds depends mainly on the composition of the catalyst and the temperature of the process. Aniline is well adsorbed on the acid sites of the catalyst. The presence

of aluminum, zinc and chromium oxides in the composition of the catalyst promotes the dehydration of 2-aminophenylethanol and ethylene glycol.

With an increase in temperature from 380 to 460 °C, an increase in the yield of 2,3-dehydroindole and indole is observed (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Effect of temperature on the yield of indole (1) and 2,3-dihydroindole (2).
CHA catalyst; volumetric feed rate of raw materials 0.1 hour⁻¹; ratio C₆H₄NH₂: C₂H₄(OH)₂ = 2:1

A further increase in temperature leads to a decrease in the yield of target products due to the occurrence of side reactions - polymerization, decomposition, etc.

This is proved by thermodynamic calculations for gross processes:

$$\Delta H_{298} = 15 \text{ kcal/mol}; \Delta S_{298} = 54.28 \text{ cal/mol};$$

$$\Delta G_{298} = -552 \text{ cal/mol}; \Delta G_{698} = -22692 \text{ cal/mol}$$

As can be seen, the heterocyclization reaction of aniline with ethylene glycol has an endothermic effect and is difficult to implement under normal conditions.

The decrease in the Gibbs energy with increasing temperature also confirms that the yield of target products increases with increasing temperature (Table 3).

Table 3

Influence of the $C_6H_5NH_2 : C_2H_4(OH)_2$ Ratio on the Indole Yield.
 $T = 460\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $v = 0.1\text{ hour}^{-1}$

№	Ratio (mol) $C_6H_5NH_2 : C_2H_4(OH)_2$	Yield from theory, %		Condensation $C_2H_4(OH)_2$
		Indole	2,3-dihydroindole	
1.	1:1	23,0	16,0	70
2.	2:1	28,0	18,0	76
3.	3:1	32,5	21,0	82
4.	4:1	36,0	24,0	87
5.	5:1	40,5	26,0	93
6.	6:1	42,5	22,0	98

From the data in Table 3 it can be seen that the optimal ratio of $C_6H_5NH_2 : C_2H_4(OH)_2$ is 4-6:1 mol. In this case, the yield of indole is 36-42%, and 2,3-dihydroindole - 22-24% of theory. Ethylene glycol conversion is 87-98%. Based on the results obtained, we proposed the following scheme for the formation of indole and 2,3-dihydroindole structures from aniline and ethylene glycol:

a) absorption of aniline on the surface of the catalyst:

b) dehydration of ethylene glycol with the formation of ethylene oxide:

c) condensation of ethylene oxide with adsorbed aniline to form 2-aminophenylethanol:

The formation of 2-aminophenylethanol has been proven by counter synthesis. Alkylation of aniline with diethanolamine in the liquid phase in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid was carried out. The reaction goes according to the scheme:

The resulting 2-aminophenylethanol was passed through the catalyst at a temperature of 420–460°C. It has been established that the yield of indole and 2,3-dihydroindole is 8-10% higher than when passing a mixture of aniline with diethylene glycol. The formation of indole and 2,3-dihydroindole from 2-aminophenylethanol in the presence of polyfunctional catalysts with dehydration and dehydrocyclization properties proceeds through the formation of N-vinyl aniline.

The dehydrogenation of 2,3-dihydroindole to indole proceeds only in the presence of zinc and chromium oxides in the composition of the catalysts. It has been shown that in the presence of catalysts containing zinc and chromium oxides less than 10% (in total), 2,3-dihydroindole is not completely dehydrogenated:

Based on the experimental data obtained, it can be concluded that the rate-limiting step in the formation of indole from aniline and ethylene glycol is the step of dehydrogenation of 2,3-dihydroindole to indole.

Conclusion: In order to develop effective single-stage methods, the reactions of heterocyclization of nitrogen-containing compounds with hydroquinone, the catalytic synthesis of compounds of the indole series, based on aniline and ethylene glycol, were studied. The formations of 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-thione with a yield of 92% and 5-hydroxy-1,3-benzoxo-2-one with a yield of 92-94 % of theory were synthesized and proved. 11 new efficient catalytic systems for the synthesis of indole and its derivatives have been developed: the formation of 2,3-dihydroindole (24%) and indole (42%) has been proven. The optimal process conditions are found and a probable scheme of the stage of formation of the above products is proposed.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПРОЦЕССОВ КОНДИЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ ВОЗДУХА НА СУДАХ-БАЛКЕРАХ

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OPTIMIZATION OF AIR CONDITIONING PROCESSES ON BULK CARRIERS SHIPS

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Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены основные задачи кондиционирования воздуха на морских транспортных судах. Освещены процессы и режимы тепло-влажностной обработки воздуха и факторы влияющие на организм человека. Приведены данные медико-санитарных и эксплуатационных исследований систем кондиционирования воздуха. Приведены санитарные нормы по качеству воздуха для судовых жилых и общественных помещений. Рассмотрены особенности и возникающие сложности в эксплуатации систем кондиционирования воздуха на судах-балкерах. Приведены рекомендации для обеспечения оптимального режим работы судовых систем кондиционирования воздуха на судах-балкерах в период грузовых операций.

Abstract

The article considers the main tasks of air conditioning on sea transport ships. The processes and regimes of heat-moisture treatment of air and factors affecting the human body are highlighted. The data of medical and sanitary and operational studies of air conditioning systems are given. Sanitary standards for air quality for ship-board residential and public premises are given. The features and emerging difficulties in the operation of air conditioning systems on bulk carriers are considered. Recommendations are given to ensure the optimal operation of ship air conditioning systems on bulk carrier ships during cargo operations.

Ключевые слова: кондиционер, кислород, воздух, фильтр, заслонка, температура, испарение, поверхность.

Keywords: air conditioning, oxygen, air, filter, damper, temperature evaporation, surface.

Поддержание в помещениях судна наиболее благоприятного климата является сложной и важной задачей, так как обеспечивает нормальные